
REFINING SHARELM: PLUGIN EXPANSION, SYNTHETIC ANNOTATION, AND DATASET ANALYSIS

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ABSTRACT

As part of the EleutherAI open AI summer research this year, we worked on expanding the ShareLM browser extension and dataset, by adding support to collecting conversations from multiple models, in addition to redesigning some of the visual parts of the extension, in the mean time conducted several analysis, and feature engineering using an LLM to synthesize features on the ShareLM dataset, and extract insight regarding the models, users, the conversations and the relations connecting them, then suggesting further improvements and uses cases of the dataset, besides fine-tuning large language models. the browser extension repository at: <https://github.com/shachardon/share-lm>, and the data analysis code can be found at: https://github.com/Samir-atra/share-lm_dataset_analysis

Keywords Data analysis · Dataset · Natural language processing · feature engineering

1 Introduction

Instruction tuning is a method to improve and structure the information of post-training a LLM, and the data [1] used for this purpose needs to be high quality [2], in comparison to the pre-training data. Since there are many use cases for an LLM, there is a wide variety of instruction tuning datasets [3] such as 1) Question-Answer, 2) image-description, 3) language translation, 4) conversations. diving into more details, types of conversations that might take place are between 1) human-human, 2) AI model -

AI model [4], and 3) human - AI model [5], where the first is the most common type and can be found by scraping conversations from the internet [6] [7] on the internet, messages, emails and social media besides many other platforms and formats, and usually get used in pre-training the models, while the AI model- AI model conversation might not be fit for use in fine tuning a model, since it might have all types of weaknesses a model can have from the lack of reason, diverging from the topic, hallucinating, and other issues that rise during the conversation and do not get noticed.

The third type, is the conversations taking place between the AI model and a human user, on many occasions, most commonly in the commercial models websites such as ChatGPT², Claude³, and HuggingFace chat⁴. On each of these websites, several models are available for chatting, reasoning, searching the web, summarizing, and analyzing long texts. The resulting conversations are of high quality because they are often managed or guided by a human (at one end), which helps maintain focus on the same topic and a single, coherent context.

1.1 ShareLM chrome extension

Prior to this work a Google Chrome browser extension was built [8], to collect conversations from a group of websites and the LLMs available on them, including the ChatGPT, Claude and HuggingFaceChat model and any HuggingFace model integrated to a Gradio interface [9], where these conversations get detected from the browser interface element and recorded from the CSS selectors for the user message and the model message, and ordered in a format of a prompt-response conversations for as many turns and sessions as the user interact with the LLM.

²<https://chatgpt.com/>

³<https://claude.ai/new>

⁴<https://huggingface.co/chat>

In addition to the conversation, some metadata get collected about the user, including the age, and gender, and for the conversation the rate, language and toxicity [10]. besides other features, that part of it needs to be provided manually by the user and others get collected autonomously by the browser extension.

Another main part of the browser extension is the user interface, and banner which indicates the operability of the extension and enables the user to fill some of the metadata in addition to other uses.

1.2 ShareLM dataset

The ShareLM dataset [11]⁵ is available in its latest version on HuggingFace with around 3.5M human - model multilingual and multi-turn conversations, some of the languages included in the dataset are: 1) English 2) Arabic, 3) Hebrew, 4) Portuguese, 5) Spanish besides others. in addition to code debugging prompts, and mathematics problems related prompts, and as in appendix A, partially were collected using the browser extension and another part were added from datasets such as Anthropic/hh-rlhf [12] and PRISM-alignment [13], besides many other sources and datasets.

The dataset conversations are in a wide range of languages, turn counts, and lengths. with a wide variety of topics and arguments. and the features of the dataset are as in the Table 1:

The two metadata features, have many sub-features that include fine details about the user and the conversation, and can be found listed in Tables 2 and 3 where the user features are the manual entries for the plugin interface, and the conversation features are mainly inferred from the conversation, manually entered by the user or autonomously generated.

The main contribution of this work is that we improve many aspects of the ShareLM extension and dataset:

1. Add support for several models and websites to allow the extension to collect user-model conversations.
2. Improve the banner design to be more efficient and fit a wider range of websites.
3. Add a new synthetic sub-feature to the conversation metadata, to classify the topic of the conversation, in an automated process.
4. Analyze the dataset to find best way possible to improve the browser extension and the dataset, with possibility for driving social and business insights.

The next parts of the article are structured in the sections: 2 Analysis and expansion, 4 Possible automations, 5 Conclusion.

⁵<https://huggingface.co/datasets/shachardon/ShareLM>

2 Analysis and expansion

Collecting a dataset is enhanced by having a larger number of features and a wider range of representations of real-world phenomena [14], which enriches the dataset's underlying distribution. consequently, enables the model that trains on it to have better performance on a wider variety of tasks, and based on this hypotheses several improvements were made.

2.1 Chrome extension expansion

An expansion to the ShareLM chrome extension was made by contributing to the repository⁶, mainly through using Jules: an async development agent by Google⁷, included adding more websites and models for the list of sources of conversations collected, and to fit a wider range of users and preferences.

The models were added are: Gemini⁸, Mistral LeChat⁹, Perplexity¹⁰, Poe¹¹ and Cohere playground chat¹²,

In addition to the platforms that includes many models, especially Poe, minor changes to the extension banner design and GitHub¹³ repository was applied.

2.2 Dataset analysis

Despite the dataset is built for training and tuning models, by observing the features included, we get motivated to analyze and inspect the data for any patterns and insights that can be found, so starting by individual features, can find that *the human user* does not get identified by their name, or any other personal information, but by a User ID that is generated by an algorithm designed to produce the same ID for the same initial name, while the other features included for the user under the metadata column, get manually and optionally inputted by the user, are *location*, *age*, and *gender*, and one possible use of this data might be finding the activity of the extension, and models based on the location, age group and gender, but due to the fact that it is not a required field from the user, only a few insertions to the dataset include this information, which invalidates any conclusions based on them.

For the information included about *the model*, only the Model name is available, and it can be used to derive many insights when visualized with the information about the users or the conversations, but currently that comes with limitations due to the inaccuracy in registering the model name from the website such as inserting "LMarena.ai" for

⁶<https://github.com/shachardon/share-lm>

⁷<https://jules.google/>

⁸<https://gemini.google.com/app>

⁹<https://chat.mistral.ai/chat>

¹⁰<https://www.perplexity.ai/>

¹¹<https://poe.com/>

¹²<https://dashboard.cohere.com/playground/chat>

¹³<https://github.com/shachardon/share-lm>

Feature	Description
Conversation ID	Autonomously generated encrypted phrase, unique for every conversation.
Conversation	The contents of the textual human-model conversation.
Model name	The display name of the model (ChatGPT, Claude, Gemini).
User ID	Autonomously generated encrypted phrase, unique for every user.
Time stamp	The time when the conversation took place
Source	The source of the conversation, and from which dataset it was taken
User metadata	Further information and details about the user
Conversation metadata	Further details and description for the conversation

Table 1: ShareLM dataset features

Sub-feature	Description
Location	Geographical location of the user
Age	An integer for representing the users age
Gender	The gender of the user

Table 2: User metadata

all the models available on the platform without specifying the type of the model in use.

The Third main element of the dataset is *the conversation*, which makes the majority of the data, where the provided information is a conversation ID, as mentioned in the Table 1, and the conversation is fully recorded as prompt-response pairs between the user and the model, which can be regarding any topic or in any type of language, and in any length.

In addition, to the features present in the dataset, feature engineering [15] was conducted, specifically on the conversation metadata mentioned in Table 3, we autonomously [16] added a *synthetic* eighth sub-feature to the conversation metadata, describing the **"topic"** of the conversation [17], and this addition was made to enable better improvement by better understand the conversation, particularly when observed in conjunction with other features, as will be explained in the following sections, visualizing the topic against the model or the times of occurrences, For testing and validation, adding this feature included 10K rows of the dataset, therefore using an LLM to infer the topic of the conversation [18] was more efficient and scalable, to have a representative annotation, five classes were selected [19] to describe the topic:

- Assisting/creative writing.
- Analysis/decision.
- Explanation/coding.
- Factual info.
- Math reason.

Classifying the conversations was done by a **gemma-3n-e2b-it** [20], implemented using the Google GenAI library

¹⁴, and the full code can be found in the data analysis repository ¹⁵, choosing this model came because it is the latest in its size, and available to classify, 15K conversations everyday, with minimal resources requirement.

2.3 Visualizations

We filtered the improved dataset to include only rows with a non-empty *model name*, yielding approximately 10,000 relevant entries. Following this, we integrated the topic sub-feature to enrich the data structure, which enabled the generation of the following analyses:

2.3.1 Contributions per user

The number of contributions made by each user, or the frequency of usage for the dataset: can be found by counting the conversations submitted by each User ID, and as in figure 1

Figure 1: Contribution per user

The plot reveals that user retention is limited, with only a small fraction of users contributing significantly, with the highest count reaching more than 850. This disparity results in a narrow range of topics and a concentration

¹⁴<https://googleapis.github.io/python-genai>

¹⁵https://github.com/Samir-atra/share-lm-dataset_analysis

Sub-feature	Description
Rate	Zero(s) or one(s) numerically representing a like or a dislike, respectively, assigned by the user to the conversation.
Language	The language used in the conversation.
Redacted	Flag indicating if any content in the conversation was redacted for privacy/safety.
Toxic	The value measured for the toxicity of the conversation.
Title	The title of the conversation.
Custom instruction	A boolean to indicate if a custom instruction (or system message) was used when the conversation was made.
Status	Indicate the conversation’s progress through quality control pipeline after being collected.

Table 3: Conversation metadata

of usage on a small number of high-frequency models. Consequently, strategies to enhance engagement—such as redesigning the extension, increasing promotion, and introducing incentives—are required to stimulate user contribution and interaction.

2.3.2 Conversation length

A very important measure for datasets when it comes to training models, is knowing the lengths of the conversations included in the dataset, which get measured by the *number of turns* i.e. pairs of prompt-response between the user and the model, and there are other methods of measurements such as the number of characters, number of tokens, or the number of words.

Figure 2: Conversation length, **Left:** the conversation number of turns against the frequency, **Right:** a scatter plot for the conversation number of turns against the conversation index

The plot 2 for the conversation length analysis can indicate the following facts about the data samples analyzed:

- The longest conversation is a single one with around a hundred turn and the shortest has a single turn only.
- The majority of conversations are below 20 turns.
- The turn count with highest occurrences is the 2 turns conversation reaching around 3000 in frequency.

these findings can indicate the high efficiency for the models used and the users are of a specific group instead of a wide range.

2.3.3 Model counts

The model counts can help in understanding the users of the plugin and which model they prefer, and currently the model names are not precise, and as mentioned in a previous section.

The plot in figure 3 shows:

- One model which is GPT4 [21] is dominating the use with around 250 conversations.
- The more frequently used models are only 12 and 6 of them are GPT [21] [22] models by OpenAI.
- LMArena.ai¹⁶ is heavily used being in the second place. Worth noting, although there are tens of models on the website all of them are listed under the same model name.

2.3.4 Topic counts

For the topic counting and visualization, the classes were used are the same as in the “WildChat” dataset, and they are as specified above in section 2.2, applying the classification on the conversations of the dataset shows the following:

- Analysis/decision and factual info classes are the *most common* in the dataset with more than 7000 conversations.
- Assistance and deployment classes are not part of the criteria but can be found in one occurrence each in the dataset.
- Math reasoning is almost non-existent in the dataset.
- “explanation” and “creative writing” have separate frequencies, and get summed with the main classes, to have more accurate and representative numbers.

¹⁶<https://lmarena.ai/>

Figure 3: Model use frequency

Figure 4: topics frequency

2.3.5 Topic per model

To better understand the user patterns, and how each model is related to a conversation topic or a use case, conducted an analysis of the topic vs. model name, as in figure 5

- GPT4 [21] which has the highest number in usage frequency is used for finding factual info, analysis/decision and explanation/coding.

- LMArena is mostly used for conversations under the analysis/decision topic, which has the second highest usage frequency.
- ChatGPT comes third with a topic pattern similar to the GPT4 model which indicates that a similar user types are the ones interested in GPT models.

These insights shows that the main use case of the model is analysis and decision-making assistance, which gives a

Figure 5: Topics for each model

general category for the dataset sample for which the topic was added, and reflects the interest of users, in addition to providing understanding and drive future development for the extension.

3 Suggested improvements

The dataset’s comprehensive structure, featuring a rich set of features and sub-features, makes it highly useful for both instruction tuning language models, across a wide range of applications and for *facilitating research studies* in various fields, including the humanities.

Starting with the browser extension, and to improve the efficiency of the user metadata collection process to have a fully annotated dataset and more useful set of features, the upgrade of the design of the browser extension to have the *user metadata insertion as a requirement* instead of having it as an optional addition.

Due to the importance of the model name feature as part of the dataset for model training and for further research, such as customer satisfaction and preference, and due to the increasing number of models available, we suggest changing the detection of the model name, to be from the user interface temporarily and have an accurate model name feature.

Given that the speed of data collection and the size of the dataset present significant challenges, enhancing the user interface to be more intuitive and streamlined is a critical goal for driving further advancement.

To have a wider range of features and increase engagement from a broader user base, adding support to models on educational platforms and AI tutors should be of interest, in addition to collecting conversations from help and website navigation assistants, integrated to all types of websites.

4 Possible automation

Annotating the data to have a complete and understandable set of instructions to be used for training, is an essential part of creating the dataset, but due to the long time and amount of effort required, we suggest automating the process [23] [24] by using fine-tuned LLMs tested for high performance in the application, and classification, which will deliver less accurate but quick results, clarifying the path for more structured improvement to the dataset, and browser extension. or could be used in studies and estimations that do not necessitate high accuracy.

4.1 Adding features

The current incompleteness of several key metadata features in the dataset, which are dependent on the associated conversational context, represents a significant bottleneck for feature engineering. To transform the raw dialogue into actionable, structured data, we propose using a large language model (LLM) for automated data enrichment. This LLM—either a high-throughput commercial service or a cost-effective, task-optimized open-source model fine-tuned for conversational metadata extraction—will parse the conversations to fill the sparse features like topic, senti-

ment, language or title, thereby unlocking the full potential of the dataset for specialized machine learning research.

4.1.1 Language classification

The “language” sub-feature reported in Table 3 is currently unpopulated and thus requires completion. Given that multilingualism constitutes a key capability of large language models, iteratively augmenting the conversations with prompts that elicit language identification inferences can enhance the overall usability and analytical value of the dataset.

4.1.2 Creating titles

Similar to the process described in the previous sub section, completing the “title” sub-feature can give a shortcut to understanding the conversations, and serving as an extra short summary, which might be used for fine tuning the models on another task, that is popular now a days.

4.1.3 Completing the model name

Instead of inferencing the language and creating a title based on the conversation, can use the “source” sub-feature to infer the “model name” sub feature, especially knowing that many datasets were added to the ShareLM dataset, generated by known models mentioned in their research articles.

4.2 Extracting further insights

Further insights can be extracted from the dataset in case of having a complete metadata and all the features, which can be used in developing a deeper understanding to the users and drive the future improvements of the browser extension and the models used:

- Related to the **users**: finding each users favorite model and how often they use it or switch to use another, and looking for patterns of use for each user regarding the time of usage. In addition to finding the location of the widest group of users, the most contributing age group, and gender.
- Regarding the **model**: Find the rate-to-model ratio (user engagement), which regardless of the rating value, which can be used to assess the model, this ratio can improve the understanding of the user behavior of each model and how interactive they are. In addition, having an accurate model name can help estimate the toxicity-per-model, and which model needs improvement in this regard. and finding the language-to-model use while having a rating by the user can help evaluate the multilingual performance of the models, supported by the regional favorite and the age group using the specific model.
- For the **conversation**: visualizing the rate against the language can give an indication for the multi-

linguality performance for a certain model, while visualizing the language against the toxicity, might also help in measuring the toxicity for a specific model in a language for a study in machine translation and multi-linguality, in addition to other studies that can be found by visualizing one of the conversation metadata against one of the feature of the dataset and according to the use case it is done for.

5 Conclusion

This research establishes a novel and viable path for the collection and creation of high-quality datasets, specifically for the post-training refinement of large language models (LLMs). Furthermore, the resulting dataset holds significant potential for advancing interdisciplinary study and research within the humanities and social sciences.

The work also proposes a robust methodology aimed at explaining how commercial LLMs operate, specifically by analyzing the relationship between these models, the companies that make them, and the resulting user conversations.

Finally, the study introduces and suggests a set of automated methods for easily expanding both web applications and various datasets. These methods use LLMs to create synthetic data and generate new features, which allows for highly scalable data practices.

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A Classification prompt

The prompt that was used for generating the topic of the conversation using the model and the process mentioned in section 2, is:

```
1 Prompt: f"""Analyze the following
conversation text and classify it as
one of the following classes in the
comma-separated list [assisting/
creative writing, analysis/decision,
explanation/coding, factual info,
math reason]. Return ONLY one word
referring to the label. Conversation:
{conversation}"""
```

Listing 1: Gemma-3n-e2b-it prompt

which is a zero-shot, single paragraph prompt, and further improvements can be using a few-shot prompt or a chain-of-thought, to analyze the conversation and generate a topic.